

What is the volume, nature and diversity of research on interventions for people experiencing homelessness that impact on health and healthcare use? A protocol for an evidence and gap map (EGM).

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Background

Over the past decade, rates of homelessness have risen in the UK and globally, with this trend predicted to continue (Office for National Statistics 2025; Watts-Cobbe et al. 2025; House of Commons Library 2025; National Alliance to End Homelessness 2025; FEANTSA 2024). Homelessness is often defined broadly, encompassing people sleeping rough, those living in temporary accommodation, and less visible forms such as ‘sofa-surfing’ (NICE 2022). It is increasingly recognised as a public health priority, rather than solely a housing issue (NICE 2022). The relationship between homelessness and health appears to be bidirectional, with poor health often a contributory factor to a person becoming homeless (Groundswell 2020), while existing illness can be exacerbated by stress, poverty and adverse living conditions. People experiencing homelessness have significantly worse health outcomes than the general population, with 81% reporting a physical health condition and 77% describing issues with mental health (Homeless Link 2025). Homelessness is linked to an increased risk of acute illness (e.g., soft tissue infections, dental caries), chronic conditions (such as diabetes, HIV, tuberculosis, cardiovascular disease, serious mental illness, epilepsy and cancer), as well as premature frailty and mortality (Fornaro et al. 2022; Barry, Ensign, and Lippek 2002; Rogans-Watson et al. 2020; Funk et al. 2022). Moreover, people experiencing homelessness are often affected by multiple health conditions, with trimorbidity (co-occurring physical and mental illness alongside substance use disorders) particularly prevalent (Chilman et al. 2025).

Fragmented or siloed services may make access to healthcare for individuals with multiple conditions particularly challenging (Jagpal et al. 2020). Furthermore, health concerns may remain unaddressed due to barriers accessing care including fear of stigma, discrimination, lack of trust, or strict eligibility criteria (Reilly, Ho, and Williamson 2022; Homeless Link 2025; Ashwell et al. 2025), often until issues become

critical or complex. This contributes to frequent use of emergency care, longer hospital stays, and unplanned readmissions to hospital for people experiencing homelessness (Vohra, Paudyal, and Price 2022; Onuoha and Banks 2023). Such patterns of delayed care and acute intervention have profound implications for people experiencing homelessness and for public services, placing a substantial financial burden on health and social care systems (Pleace and Culhane 2016; Pleace et al. 2013).

Homelessness is a complex issue, and addressing the associated health inequalities will require a systems-based approach. A coordinated response needs to consider the multiple determinants and interacting factors linked to the experience of homelessness, such as housing stability, poverty, stigma and discrimination, trauma, substance use and serious mental illness (Garcia, Doran, and Kushel 2024; Fowler et al. 2019). Strategies to improve health outcomes for people experiencing homelessness encompass tailored approaches to care coordination, such as case management (Ponka et al. 2020; Weightman et al. 2023), alongside interventions targeting housing (Aubry et al. 2020; Peng et al. 2020), income assistance (Calhoun et al. 2025), employment (Marshall et al. 2022), mental health and addiction support (Hyun, Noh, and Bae 2019; O'Leary, Coren, and Roberts 2025). Other approaches aim to minimise barriers to healthcare engagement through outreach delivery, such as street/mobile teams, specialist services in day centres or hostels (Kopanitsa et al. 2023), or through use of digital technologies (Polillo et al. 2021). Despite the implementation of numerous policy initiatives and strategies within the UK and internationally, rates of homelessness and associated health disparities continue to rise (National Alliance to End Homelessness 2025; Homeless Link 2025). Identifying interventions that lead to successful health outcomes, such as increased engagement with health services, shorter hospital stays, reduced emergency department attendance, and fewer unplanned admissions, is critical to help reduce health inequalities for people experiencing homelessness (Jagpal et al., 2020). Policymakers, commissioners and service providers, require a clear and accessible overview of the evidence base to guide resource allocation, and to inform the design and delivery of effective interventions for people experiencing homelessness.

Justification for an evidence and gap map (EGM)

Our scoping searches identified existing evidence and gap maps (EGMs) on homelessness (Singh et al. 2024; Ingram et al. 2024; Singh et al. 2025; Shepherd-Banigan et al. 2022); however, none have solely focused on interventions and their impact on health and healthcare use. Existing EGMs have had a narrower scope: Shepherd-Banigan et al. (2022) considered primary care strategies in people experiencing homelessness with serious mental illness, Patel et al. (2024) focused on interventions with quality of life outcomes, and Ingram et al. (2024) included studies published in the Republic of Ireland only. Two EGMs produced by the Centre for

Homelessness Impact (Singh et al. 2025; Singh et al. 2024) have a much broader scope than our planned EGM, including studies examining housing stability, crime and employment, in addition to health outcomes.

Our EGM would build on existing work (Singh et al. 2025; Singh et al. 2024; Ingram et al. 2024; Shepherd-Banigan et al. 2022) with the creation of a standalone homelessness and health evidence and gap map. An EGM centred on health outcomes would allow for more detailed categorisation of interventions and their impacts. This enhanced granularity would enable decision-makers, funders and researchers to more easily identify the evidence for interventions that impact on health and identify critical gaps where further primary research or evidence is required.

Overall aim and objectives of the EGM

To identify and map evidence on interventions that impact on health outcomes, healthcare access, use and associated costs for people experiencing homelessness.

To meet this aim, we will develop an evidence and gap map (EGM). EGMs are a systematic evidence synthesis product that provide a visual representation of available research on a topic (Campbell et al. 2023). Their purpose is to make research evidence more accessible to users, including researchers, policymakers, commissioners and other stakeholders, supporting the identification of areas for synthesis where there is a surplus of studies, or highlighting where further primary research is needed (Campbell et al. 2023; Khalil et al. 2025; Snilstveit et al. 2016; White et al. 2020). Members of the project advisory group (PAG) and experts working in this field have indicated that a map specifically focussed on health outcomes is much needed.

The specific objectives of this EGM are to:

- Identify and map relevant systematic reviews, randomised controlled trials (RCTs) and other types of comparative study that investigate the *effectiveness* of interventions.
- Identify and map qualitative studies relating to the *experiences* of interventions that impact on health outcomes or healthcare use.
- Identify areas where there is a surplus of primary studies investigating similar interventions to inform whether future systematic reviews may be helpful.
- Identify evidence gaps where further primary research is needed.
- Identify gaps and evidence related to health equity.

Research question:

What is the volume, nature and diversity of research on interventions for people with experience of homelessness that impact on health and healthcare use?

Methods

The methods to produce an EGM are similar to a systematic review, with key steps including: the development of inclusion/exclusion criteria, a comprehensive search for evidence, application of rigorous and transparent methods for the selection of studies and data extraction (White et al. 2020). We will consult good practice guidance for the conduct and reporting of EGMs (White et al. 2020; Snilstveit et al. 2016; Khalil et al. 2025).

Framework development

The framework for the EGM will be presented with two dimensions, with intervention categories appearing on rows, and outcome domains on columns. We will consult policy documents, key literature and related EGMs, to identify existing typologies or frameworks of interventions and health outcome domains for people experiencing homelessness (Singh et al. 2024; EPOC 2015; FEANTSA 2023). We will use an iterative approach to the development of the framework. Intervention categories and outcome domains will be adapted following pilot coding of an initial sample of included studies, and through consultation with both our Project Advisory Group (PAG) and Patient and Public Involvement and Engagement (PPIE) team, ensuring our framework meets the needs of intended users of the EGM.

Inclusion and exclusion criteria

The inclusion and exclusion criteria to be applied to studies identified through searches is outlined in Table 1:

Eligibility criteria	Included	Excluded
Population/ Types of participants	<p>People described as experiencing homelessness (PEH) who:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • are sleeping rough, • are temporary residents of hostels, B&Bs, local authority or privately managed accommodation, domestic violence shelters, and other types of temporary accommodation, • are obliged to stay temporarily with other people or ‘sofa surfing’, • are squatting (occupying empty, disused or abandoned property), • are described as ‘at risk’ of homelessness (included if the population is both PEH and those ‘at risk’) • are described as vulnerably/unstably housed. <p>In qualitative studies of experiences of interventions, study participants could be service providers, clinicians, healthcare professionals engaging with PEH.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PEH due to natural disaster (for e.g., hurricane, flooding or earthquake). • Children or adolescents described as ‘runaways’ unless specified as homeless. • Studies including a mix of PEH and other vulnerable groups.
Interventions	<p>Any health, social care, financial or housing intervention that has been developed, modified or introduced with the intention of improving physical or mental health outcomes, or access to healthcare, that specifically targets PEH.</p>	<p>Interventions without an objective to improve health outcomes or access to healthcare for PEH. Studies of existing/baseline healthcare services (e.g. experiences of emergency care).</p>
Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mortality • <i>Physical health outcomes, including but not limited to:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Biological markers of disease control (e.g. viral load) ○ Cardiovascular (e.g. stroke, myocardial infarctions) ○ Diabetes and complications ○ Respiratory (e.g. asthma or COPD exacerbations) ○ Gastrointestinal and renal (e.g. liver disease, cirrhosis, hepatitis, chronic kidney disease) ○ Nutritional (e.g. malnutrition, sarcopenia) ○ Skin (e.g. infections, wound healing) ○ Dental/oral health (e.g. caries) ○ Sexual health (e.g. HIV, STIs, use of contraception) ○ Maternal health/pregnancy health outcomes (e.g. low birthweight, preterm birth) ○ Functional health (e.g. mobility, physical functioning, frailty, injuries, fractures, falls, activities of daily living) ○ Chronic symptoms (e.g. pain, fatigue) • <i>Mental health/psychological outcomes, including but not limited to:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Depression/mood disorders ○ Anxiety disorders (e.g. OCD, GAD, PTSD) ○ Suicide and self-harm ○ Schizophrenia/psychosis ○ Addiction (e.g. drug or alcohol) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Crime, criminalisation, arrests or imprisonment, recidivism or repeat offending • Perceived safety • Housing stability, housing status or satisfaction with accommodation • Employment status, earned income, or access to welfare benefits • Life skills or food/money management • Academic attainment • Stigma • Health knowledge, attitudes to health • Self-esteem, self-worth, resilience • Happiness, well-being without a health measure, life-satisfaction • Loneliness, isolation, social network size, community integration, social integration, sense of community, connectedness

Phenomenon of Interest	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Stress ○ Well-being related to health ○ Self-efficacy (if related to health behaviour or management of a condition) ○ 'Recovery' if related to health (e.g. recovery from a mental illness, or a substance use disorder) ● <i>Health-related quality of life</i> ● <i>Cognitive health outcomes</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Cognitive health (e.g. memory, cognition, executive function) ● <i>Health behaviours</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Drinking, smoking, drug use, risky behaviour, dietary intake, physical activity ● <i>Structural health outcomes</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Health service use (e.g. GP visits, hospitalisations, A&E attendance, ambulance call outs, attendance at screening clinics) and associated costs ○ Cost-effectiveness <p><i>Experiences of receiving or delivering an intervention as described by PEH, health care professionals or service providers that reports an impact on health outcomes.</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Outcomes that relate to implementation feasibility, fidelity, recruitment, retention or attrition of participants ● Experiences of an intervention that do not relate to health outcomes
Study designs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Systematic reviews. To be included as a systematic review, the review must report: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ A clearly defined research question ○ A reproducible search strategy, including sources and date searched ○ Defined inclusion/exclusion criteria and methods for study selection, quality appraisal and data synthesis ● <i>Experimental</i> studies, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ randomised controlled trials (RCTS) ○ non-randomised studies ○ quasi-experimental studies ○ before-and-after studies ○ economic evaluations ● <i>Observational</i> studies with a control group, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Case-control ○ Cohort ○ Cross-sectional ○ Retrospective ● Qualitative studies investigating experiences of an intervention using interviews or focus groups ● Cost studies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Scoping reviews, evidence and gap maps (EGMs), overviews of reviews, umbrella reviews, rapid reviews, realist reviews. ● Systematic reviews of experimental or observational studies without a comparison or not evaluating interventions ● Empty systematic reviews ● Narrative reviews or literature reviews ● Modelling studies ● Case series ● Case reports ● Systematic review protocols or clinical trial registrations
Publication types	Journal articles, dissertations or theses, reports, or grey literature reporting included study designs	Conference abstracts, letters, comments, editorials, opinion
Geographical locations	All geographical locations	No restriction based on geography

Settings	Interventions delivered in any setting, including but not limited to online, mobile clinics, day centres, shelters, temporary accommodation, community-based settings, GP practices or other non-specialist primary care services, specialist health centres for PEH, emergency care, A&E or hospital settings	No restriction on setting of intervention delivery
Language	All languages	No restriction based on language
Publication date	All publication dates from database inception to search date	No restriction on publication date

Search methods and sources

We will search the following databases from inception with no restriction on publication date.

- MEDLINE (Ovid)
- PsycINFO (Ovid)
- Global Health (Ovid)
- Social Policy and Practice (Ovid)
- Health Management Information Consortium (HMIC) (Ovid)
- CINAHL Ultimate (EBSCOhost)
- British Nursing Collection, including British Nursing Index (ProQuest)
- ASSIA (ProQuest)
- Web of Science Core Collection (Clarivate Analytics)
- Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews (Wiley)
- Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials (CENTRAL) (Wiley)

Provisional search strategies have been developed by Information Specialists (NS/MR) in consultation with the review team. The search strategy will combine terms for homelessness and relevant study designs (i.e. systematic reviews, RCTs, non-randomised studies, observational studies, or qualitative research), using controlled vocabulary where available (e.g. MeSH in MEDLINE) and free-text searching. Terms for the population (i.e., people experiencing homelessness) have been adapted from search strategies used for the NICE guideline (NICE 2022). The provisional search strategy for Ovid MEDLINE is available in Appendix 1.

Supplementary search methods

Citation chasing

Forward and backwards citation searching will be carried out on key papers using CitationChaser (Haddaway, Grainger, and Gray 2022). The reference lists of key systematic reviews will also be checked for additional studies.

Handsearching

Key journals identified during searches will be hand-searched.

Grey literature

We anticipate that some empirical studies, especially qualitative literature, may be reported in the grey literature and not published in academic journals. We intend to capture this content via database searches of ProQuest Dissertations & Theses, searches of Google, Google Scholar and BASE (Bielefeld Academic Search Engine), and through searching or browsing publications available via the following websites:

- United States Interagency Council on Homelessness Homeless Hub (Canada)

- European Observatory on Homelessness
- Homelessness Australia
- National Alliance to End Homelessness (US)
- Institute of Global Homelessness
- National Coalition for the Homeless (US)
- Homeless Link (UK)
- Crisis (UK)
- Centrepoin (UK)
- Shelter (UK)
- Pathway (UK)
- Patient Experience Library (UK)

We will also search key government websites such as the Office for Health Improvement and Disparities (OHID) and Ministry of Housing, Communities and Local Government (MHCLG). Clinical trials portals (clinicaltrials.gov and the WHO International Clinical Trials Registry Platform) will be searched for ongoing trials. Ongoing trials will not be included in the EGM, but we will check studies identified via clinical trials portals for completed studies. MedRxiv will be searched for unpublished preprints.

Deduplication of search results

All search results will be imported into EndNote 2025 (Clarivate). Deduplication of all search results will be completed using EndNote functionality, manual checks and 'Deduplicator' (Forbes et al. 2024) available from TERA-Tools (<https://tera-tools.com>).

Screening and study selection

Initial study selection will be completed in EndNote 2025 (Clarivate). Two reviewers will independently screen a random sample of records (n=100) applying the inclusion/exclusion criteria. Decisions will be discussed, and screening criteria may be revised, if necessary, to ensure consistent interpretation and application.

The remaining records will be independently screened by two reviewers applying inclusion/exclusion criteria to title/abstracts. Full-text articles will be obtained for records meeting inclusion criteria or where it is unclear from information in the title/abstract alone. Two reviewers will then independently assess the eligibility of each full text article in EPPI-Reviewer 6 (EPPI-Centre Software). Disagreements between reviewers will be resolved through discussion, involving a third member of the team if necessary to reach consensus.

The selection of studies at each stage will be documented in PRISMA flowchart, and reasons for exclusion reported for each article retrieved at full text (Page et al. 2021).

Data extraction and coding

A standardised data extraction coding set will be developed in EPPI-Reviewer 6 software (EPPI-Centre Software) and piloted by two reviewers on a small sample (n=20) of included studies of different study designs (i.e. systematic review, RCT, qualitative study). The remaining data extraction and coding will be performed by one reviewer and checked by a second. PPIE team members may also contribute to coding activities. Disagreements will be resolved through discussion with a third reviewer, where necessary. The coding set may be modified following the piloting process.

The coding set, intervention categories and outcome domains, will be developed and refined in consultation with the Project Advisory Group (PAG) and PPIE Team to ensure data of interest to stakeholders and people with experience of homelessness are extracted from included studies.

The coding set will include, but is not limited to the following:

Publication information

- First author
- Publication year
- DOI

Location of study

- Region
- Country

Population characteristics

- Type of homelessness experienced (i.e., people experiencing homelessness as rough sleeping, or living in temporary accommodation, hostels, domestic violence shelter, or squatting)
- PROGRESS-Plus characteristics (including ethnicity, age, gender/sex, sexual orientation, gender reassignment, occupation, religion, socioeconomic status, disability)(Cochrane Methods Equity ; O'Neill et al. 2014)
- Other population characteristics (including ex-prisoners, veterans, immigration status, people without recourse to public funds, place of residence: urban or rural)

Intervention

- Interventions will be organised into broad categories and subcategories determined in consultation with the Project Advisory Group (PAG) and PPIE team. Intervention types include, but are not limited to, Housing First and housing provision, case management, psychosocial interventions, behavioural

and lifestyle interventions, financial assistance, employment or vocational interventions, service provider training (for e.g. training in trauma-informed approaches), tailored addiction services or supervised injection facilities, specialised homelessness healthcare services, discharge planning, mobile or outreach services, preventative health care services, and digital or telehealth interventions.

- Studies may be coded for multiple intervention types (for e.g., where interventions have multiple components)
- Other intervention characteristics, including but not limited to:
 - Delivery setting (e.g. primary care, specialist, emergency care, day centres, temporary accommodation, street)
 - Delivered by (e.g. peers, general practitioners (GPs), nurses, housing service providers, charities, social workers, clinical psychologists, emergency care health professionals)
 - Delivered to groups or individuals

Outcomes:

Studies will be coded with the health outcomes reported. Outcomes will be organised into broad domains and subdomains determined in consultation with the Project Advisory Group (PAG) and PPIE team, including:

- Mortality
- Physical health
- Mental health
- Structural outcomes: healthcare use and associated costs
- Experiences of intervention(s) related to health outcomes: service provider, health care professional, people experiencing homelessness (qualitative studies)

Study design:

Studies will be coded to indicate their study design:

- Systematic reviews
- RCTs
- Other experimental studies
- Observational studies
- Primary qualitative studies
- Economic evaluations/Cost studies

Language of publication

Once coding is completed, we will conduct data cleaning to identify any studies with uncoded data, or where codes appear to have been incorrectly applied. We will also ask our project advisory group (PAG) to explore and test the EGM prior to launch to identify any further coding issues.

Tools for assessing risk of bias/study quality

Critical appraisal is not a mandatory step for EGMs (White et al. 2020), and the quality of included studies will not be assessed. The EGM will include a range of study designs (systematic reviews, randomised controlled trials, non-randomised trials, observational studies, primary qualitative studies), and design will be indicated on the EGM.

Data analysis and presentation

EPPI-Reviewer 6/EPPI Mapper software will be used to create an online, interactive EGM, accessible by URL. This will visually represent the available evidence in a matrix with broad intervention categories (and subcategories) in rows, and health outcome domains (and subdomains) in columns. Users will be able to select 'bubbles' within cells of the matrix to see lists of studies relevant to selected outcomes and interventions. 'Bubble' diameter will be determined by the number of studies; 'bubble' colour will represent the type of studies available (i.e., systematic review, RCT).

The EGM will not provide details of the findings of systematic reviews or primary studies or provide a synthesis of primary research on interventions that impact on health outcomes or health care use.

We will publish a report to accompany the online EGM that will provide a narrative summary of key findings. The report will outline methods, summarise the volume and types of evidence across different intervention and outcome categories, and will highlight important gaps in the evidence. Tables and graphs will illustrate key findings, including, but not limited to number of studies by intervention category, outcome domains, by region or country, by publication date, by study design, or for population subgroups (e.g. women or veterans).

Filters for presentation

The EGM will offer a range of filters to allow users to identify and view studies of a certain design or for interventions delivered in a specific setting. Filter categories will be developed and refined in consultation with the Project Advisory Group (PAG) and PPIE team.

The following filter categories will include, but are not limited to:

- 1. Study location:** by world region, or individual country
- 2. Characteristics of the population:**

- a. by type of homelessness experienced (i.e., rough sleeping, living in temporary accommodation)
 - b. by PROGRESS Plus characteristics (Cochrane Methods Equity ; O'Neill et al. 2014) to enable the identification of studies of women, LGBTQ+ communities, older adults (>65 years), indigenous people)
 - c. Veterans/ex-services
 - d. Migrants, refugees
 - e. People released from prison
 - f. Comorbidities (e.g. a dual diagnosis of substance use disorder and mental illness, HIV)
- 3. Type of study:** Systematic review, randomised controlled trial, non-randomized study, observational study, economic evaluation/cost study, primary qualitative study.
- 4. Delivery setting or location of the service in relation to people experiencing homelessness:** General practice/non-specialist primary care services; specialist services; mobile clinic or street teams; telehealth; hostels; temporary accommodation; day centres; emergency departments or hospitals.

Dependency

The unit of analysis will be a report of a systematic review, RCT, other experimental study, observational study or a primary qualitative study. We will not merge multiple reports of studies, and we will not remove or exclude studies cited in systematic reviews included in the EGM. We are aware that a single primary study may be cited in multiple systematic reviews. Studies may be coded for multiple interventions or outcomes and may appear several times within the EGM.

Stakeholder engagement and PPIE

Project Advisory Group

The scope of the EGM has been developed in consultation with members of our project advisory (PAG) and public and patient involvement and engagement groups (PPIE). Our PAG includes representatives from Groundswell, an organisation in the UK that facilitates research in homelessness together with people with lived experience, as well as housing/case managers, and homelessness and health specialists. We will work closely with the PAG to develop the framework, determine intervention categories and outcome domains, and disseminate findings. We will convene four online whole project meetings over 18 months, using breakout rooms and/or collaborative tools (e.g. Miro) to share ideas and gather feedback. In between meetings, we will engage with PAG members in smaller groups or by email to ensure the developing EGM is accessible and relevant to a range of users.

Public and Patient Involvement and Engagement (PPIE)

Our PPIE activities will be facilitated by two teams: one from Groundswell in London, and another from the PPIE team at the University of Exeter. The PPIE team, which will include people with lived experience of homelessness, will play a central role in shaping the EGM by helping to identify interventions and health outcomes of interest. We will meet with the PPIE team four times throughout the project. We will provide training and support for PPIE team members who wish to contribute to EGM activities such as screening and coding data from studies. PPIE team members may choose the level and type of involvement that best suits their interests and availability.

Dissemination plans

Our Project Advisory Group (PAG) and PPIE team, incorporating health professionals, national charities, policy making bodies, and people with experience of homelessness, will be key to our dissemination activities. The developing EGM will be shared with our PAG and PPIE team members, and more widely through social media (e.g. LinkedIn), and through blog posts on the University of Exeter and Groundswell websites.

The EGM and accompanying report will be published as an academic journal article in a publication identified as relevant by stakeholders engaged in this area. We will also present findings at national conferences and regional meetings.

We will work closely with our PPIE team (including people with lived experience of homelessness) to develop a plain language summary for the final EGM.

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Data availability statement

The data that support the findings of this study will be available from the corresponding author upon request.

Declarations of interest

All authors report no declarations of interest.

Plans for updating the EGM

The EGM will be updated at the end of the project, prior to final publication. Automated searches will be set up on databases where possible. Results will be imported into

EndNote reference management software. Screening and subsequent coding with the EGM will be dependent on future funding.

References

- Ashwell, G., A. E. Williamson, M. Pattinson, and S. W. Hwang. 2025. 'Caring for patients experiencing homelessness', *BMJ*, 388: e080768.
- Aubry, T. Brcic V., A. Saad, O. Magwood, T. Abdalla, Q. Alkhateeb, E. Xie, C. Mathew, T. Hannigan, C. Costello, K. Thavorn, V. Stergiopoulos, P. Tugwell, K. Pottie, and G. Bloch. 2020. 'Effectiveness of permanent supportive housing and income assistance interventions for homeless individuals in high-income countries: a systematic review', *Lancet. Public health*, 5: e342–e60.
- Barry, P. J., J. Ensign, and S. H. Lippek. 2002. 'Embracing street culture: Fitting health care into the lives of street youth', *Journal of Transcultural Nursing*, 13: 145–52.
- Calhoun, Katherine Hoops, Julia Deziel, Erin Harrop, and Daniel Brisson. 2025. 'A systematic review of cash benefit programs for people experiencing homelessness in the United States', *Journal of Policy Practice and Research*, 6: 21–45.
- Campbell, Fiona, Andrea C. Tricco, Zachary Munn, Danielle Pollock, Ashrita Saran, Anthea Sutton, Howard White, and Hanan Khalil. 2023. 'Mapping reviews, scoping reviews, and evidence and gap maps (EGMs): the same but different—the “Big Picture” review family', *Systematic Reviews*, 12: 45.
- Chilman, Natasha, Peter Schofield, Dionne Laporte, Amy Ronaldson, and Jayati Das-Munshi. 2025. 'The prevalence of multimorbidity with mental and physical health for people who experience homelessness: a systematic review', *European Journal of Public Health: ckaf144*.
- Cochrane Methods Equity. 'PROGRESS-Plus', Accessed 18 November 2025. <https://methods.cochrane.org/equity/projects/evidence-equity/progress-plus>.
- EPOC. 2015. 'Effective practice and organisation of care (EPOC). EPOC taxonomy', Accessed 7 December 2025. <https://epoc.cochrane.org/epoc-taxonomy>.
- FEANTSA. 2023. 'Mapping healthcare in homelessness services', European Federation of National Organisations Working with the Homeless, Accessed 7th January 2026. <https://www.feantsa.org/resources/mapping-healthcare-in-homelessness-services>.
- . 2024. '9th Overview of housing exclusion in Europe', European Federation of National Organisations Working with the Homeless, Accessed 24th November 2025. <https://www.feantsa.org/resources/9th-overview-of-housing-exclusion-in-europe-2024?bcParent=27>.
- Forbes, Connor, Hannah Greenwood, Matt Carter, and Justin Clark. 2024. 'Automation of duplicate record detection for systematic reviews: Deduplicator', *Systematic Reviews*, 13: 206.
- Fornaro, M., E. Dragioti, M. De Prisco, M. Billeci, A. M. Mondin, R. Calati, L. Smith, S. Hatcher, M. Kaluziński, J. G. Fiedorowicz, M. Solmi, A. de Bartolomeis, and A. F. Carvalho. 2022. 'Homelessness and health-related outcomes: an umbrella review of observational studies and randomized controlled trials', *BMC Medicine*, 20: 224.
- Fowler, P. J., P. S. Hovmand, K. E. Marcal, and S. Das. 2019. 'Solving homelessness from a complex systems perspective: Insights for prevention responses', *Annual Review of Public Health*, 40: 465–86.

- Funk, A. M., R. N. Greene, K. Dill, and P. Valvassori. 2022. 'The impact of homelessness on mortality of individuals living in the United States: a systematic review of the literature', *Journal of Health Care for the Poor and Underserved*, 33: 457–77.
- Garcia, Cheyenne, Kelly Doran, and Margot Kushel. 2024. 'Homelessness and health: Factors, evidence, innovations that work, and policy recommendations', *Health Affairs*, 43: 164–71.
- Groundswell. 2020. 'Women, homelessness and health: a peer research project', Accessed 24 November 2025. <https://groundswell.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2020/02/Womens-Health-Research-Report.pdf>.
- Haddaway, Neal R., Matthew J. Grainger, and Charles T. Gray. 2022. 'Citationchaser: A tool for transparent and efficient forward and backward citation chasing in systematic searching', *Research Synthesis Methods*, 13: 533–45.
- Homeless Link. 2025. 'The Unhealthy State of Homelessness 2025: Findings from the Homeless Health Needs Audit', Accessed 8 December 2025. <https://homeless.org.uk/news/the-unhealthy-state-of-homelessness-2025/>.
- House of Commons Library. 2025. 'Rough sleeping in England: causes and statistics', Accessed 25 November 2025. <https://researchbriefings.files.parliament.uk/documents/SN01164/CBP10173.pdf>.
- Hyun, M., D. Noh, and S. H. Bae. 2019. 'Systematic review and meta-analyses of randomized control trials of the effectiveness of psychosocial interventions for homeless adults', *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 76: 773–86.
- Ingram, Carolyn, Conor Buggy, Darin Elabbasy, and Carla Perrotta. 2024. 'Homelessness and health-related outcomes in the Republic of Ireland: a systematic review, meta-analysis and evidence map', *Journal of Public Health*, 32: 1855–76.
- Jagpal, P., K. Saunders, G. Plahe, S. Russell, N. Barnes, R. Lowrie, and V. Paudyal. 2020. 'Research priorities in healthcare of persons experiencing homelessness: outcomes of a national multi-disciplinary stakeholder discussion in the United Kingdom', *International Journal for Equity in Health*, 19: 86.
- Khalil, Hanan, Vivian Welch, Matthew Grainger, and Fiona Campbell. 2025. 'Methodology for mapping reviews, evidence maps, and gap maps', *Research Synthesis Methods*, 16: 786–96.
- Kopanitsa, Valeriya, Stephen McWilliams, Richard Leung, Batsheva Schischa, Shazia Sarela, Sara Perelmuter, Emma Sheeran, Laure Mourgue d'Algue, Guan Chwen Tan, and Diana Margot Rosenthal. 2023. 'A systematic scoping review of primary health care service outreach for homeless populations', *Family Practice*, 40: 138–51.
- Marshall, C. A., L. Boland, L. A. Westover, R. Goldszmidt, J. Bengall, S. Aryobi, R. Isard, C. Easton, and R. Gewurtz. 2022. 'Effectiveness of employment-based interventions for persons experiencing homelessness: A systematic review', *Health & Social Care in the Community*, 30: 2142–69.
- National Alliance to End Homelessness. 2025. 'State of Homelessness 2025', Accessed 24 November 2025. <https://endhomelessness.org/state-of-homelessness/#report>.

- NICE. 2022. 'Integrated health and social care for people experiencing homelessness', National Institute for Health and Care Excellence.
<https://www.nice.org.uk/guidance/ng214/chapter/Recommendations>.
- O'Leary, C., E. Coren, and A. Roberts. 2025. 'The experiences of adults experiencing homelessness when accessing and using psychosocial interventions: A systematic review and qualitative evidence synthesis', *Campbell Systematic Reviews*, 21: e70036.
- O'Neill, J., H. Tabish, V. Welch, M. Petticrew, K. Pottie, M. Clarke, T. Evans, J. Pardo Pardo, E. Waters, H. White, and P. Tugwell. 2014. 'Applying an equity lens to interventions: using PROGRESS ensures consideration of socially stratifying factors to illuminate inequities in health', *Journal of Clinical Epidemiology*, 67: 56–64.
- Office for National Statistics. 2025. 'Homelessness in the UK: 2004 to 2024', Accessed 24 November 2025.
<https://www.ons.gov.uk/peoplepopulationandcommunity/housing/articles/ukhomelessness/2004to2024>.
- Onuoha, N., and B. Banks. 2023. 'Demographic differences in hospital readmissions, hospital length of stay and emergency room visits among homeless patients', *Annals of Family Medicine*, 21: 5478.
- Page, M. J., J. E. McKenzie, P. M. Bossuyt, I. Boutron, T. C. Hoffmann, C. D. Mulrow, L. Shamseer, J. M. Tetzlaff, E. A. Akl, S. E. Brennan, R. Chou, J. Glanville, J. M. Grimshaw, A. Hróbjartsson, M. M. Lalu, T. Li, E. W. Loder, E. Mayo-Wilson, S. McDonald, L. A. McGuinness, L. A. Stewart, J. Thomas, A. C. Tricco, V. A. Welch, P. Whiting, and D. Moher. 2021. 'The PRISMA 2020 statement: An updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews', *PLoS Medicine*, 18: e1003583.
- Patel, T., A. Martin, H. Gould, E. King, and K. Roussi. 2024. 'PCR189 What interventions have been shown to improve the quality of life in people who are homeless or have insecure housing?', *Value in Health*, 27: S543.
- Peng, Y., R. A. Hahn, R. K. Finnie, J. Cobb, S. P. Williams, J. E. Fielding, R. L. Johnson, A. E. Montgomery, A. F. Schwartz, C. Muntaner, and V. H. Garrison. 2020. 'Permanent supportive housing with housing first to reduce homelessness and promote health among homeless populations with disability: a community guide systematic review', *Journal of Public Health Management and Practice*, 26: 404–11.
- Pleace, N., I. Baptista, L. Benjaminsen, and V. Busch-Geertsema. 2013. 'The costs of homelessness in Europe: an assessment of the current evidence base', European Observatory on Homelessness, Accessed 5th December 2025.
https://www.feantsaresearch.org/download/feantsa-studies_03_web8038170339305812402.pdf.
- Pleace, N., and D. Culhane. 2016. 'Better than cure? Testing the case for enhancing prevention of single homelessness in England', *Crisis*, Accessed 24 November 2026. <https://www.crisis.org.uk/ending-homelessness/homelessness-knowledge-hub/cost-of-homelessness/better-than-cure-2016/>.
- Polillo, A., J. Sylvestre, N. Kerman, and S. Gran-Ruaz. 2021. 'The use of eHealth interventions among persons experiencing homelessness: a systematic review', *Digital Health*, 7.

- Ponka, D., C. Kendall, V. Stergiopoulos, O. Mendonca, O. Magwood, A. Saad, B. Larson, Anhr Sun, N. Arya, T. Hannigan, K. Thavorn, A. Andermann, P. Tugwell, K. Pottie, and E. Agbata. 2020. 'The effectiveness of case management interventions for the homeless, vulnerably housed and persons with lived experience: a systematic review', *PLoS One*, 15.
- Reilly, J., I. Ho, and A. Williamson. 2022. 'A systematic review of the effect of stigma on the health of people experiencing homelessness', *Health & Social Care in the Community*, 30: 2128–41.
- Rogans-Watson, R., C. Shulman, D. Lewer, M. Armstrong, and B. Hudson. 2020. 'Premature frailty, geriatric conditions and multimorbidity among people experiencing homelessness: a cross-sectional observational study in a London hostel', *Housing, Care and Support*, 23: 77–91.
- Shepherd-Banigan, Megan, Connor Drake, Jessica R. Dietch, Abigail Shapiro, Amir Alishahi Tabriz, Elizabeth E. Van Voorhees, Diya M. Uthappa, Tsai-Wei Wang, Jay B. Lusk, Stephanie Salcedo Rossitch, Jessica Fulton, Adelaide Gordon, Belinda Ear, Sarah Cantrell, Jennifer M. Gierisch, John W. Williams, and Karen M. Goldstein. 2022. 'Primary Care Engagement Among Individuals with Experiences of Homelessness and Serious Mental Illness: an Evidence Map', *Journal of general internal medicine*, 37: 1513–23.
- Singh, S. , B. Sharma, V. Nair, S. Mantri, and H. White. 2024. 'The effectiveness of interventions to improve the welfare of people experiencing and at risk of homelessness: an updated evidence and gap map', Centre for Homelessness Impact, Accessed 7 January 2026. https://uploads-ssl.webflow.com/646dd81ef095aa13072c44e0/66b1f668b86bcdd1d1895e75_CHI_EGM_FEB_2024_V4_SINGLE.pdf.
- Singh, S., B. Sharma, M. Lakshminarayanan, S. Mantri, and H. White. 2025. 'Why interventions to improve the welfare of people experiencing homelessness work or not: an updated evidence and gap map', Centre for Homelessness Impact. https://cdn.prod.website-files.com/646dd81ef095aa13072c44e0/687657c4376c104c4f71c29f_CHI_Report_2025-VFINAL%20FINAL.pdf.
- Snilstveit, B., M. Vojtkova, A. Bhavsar, J. Stevenson, and M. Gaarder. 2016. 'Evidence & Gap Maps: A tool for promoting evidence informed policy and strategic research agendas', *Journal of Clinical Epidemiology*, 79: 120–29.
- Vohra, N., V. Paudyal, and M.J. Price. 2022. 'Homelessness and the use of emergency department as a source of healthcare: A systematic review', *International Journal of Emergency Medicine*, 15: 32.
- Watts-Cobbe, B., G. Bramley, H. Pawson, G. Young, R. Sims, L. McMordie, and S. Fitzpatrick. 2025. 'The Homelessness Monitor: England 2025', Crisis, Accessed 24 November 2025. <https://www.crisis.org.uk/ending-homelessness/homelessness-monitor/the-homelessness-monitor-england-2025/>.
- Weightman, A. L., M. J. Kelson, I. Thomas, M. K. Mann, L. Searchfield, S. Willis, B. Hannigan, R. J. Smith, and R. Cordiner. 2023. 'Exploring the effect of case management in homelessness per components: A systematic review of effectiveness and implementation, with meta-analysis and thematic synthesis', *Campbell Systematic Reviews*, 19: e1329.

White, H., B. Albers, M. Gaarder, H. Kornor, J. Littell, Z. Marshall, C. Mathew, T. Pigott, B. Snilstveit, H. Waddington, and V. Welch. 2020. 'Guidance for producing a Campbell evidence and gap map', *Campbell Systematic Reviews*, 16: e1125.

Appendices

Appendix 1. Provisional search strategies

Ovid MEDLINE(R) ALL <1946 to December 04, 2025>

- 1 Ill-Housed Persons/ 10939
- 2 homeless youth/ 1533
- 3 "ill-housed persons".ti,bt,kw. 38
- 4 (homeless* or "home less").ti,bt,kw. 9953
- 5 (roofless\$ or roof less\$).ti,bt. 7
- 6 (houseless\$ or house less\$).ti,bt. 20
- 7 (un-housed or unhoused).ti,bt. 102
- 8 (sofa? adj3 surf\$).ti,bt. 2
- 9 (squat\$ adj2 (live? or living or stay\$ or temporar\$)).ti,bt. 2
- 10 squatter?.ti,bt. 114
- 11 ((rough\$ or outside) adj2 sleep\$).ti,bt. 27
- 12 (street? adj2 (sleep\$ or live? or living or dwell\$)).ti,bt. 33
- 13 "no fixed abode?".ti,bt. 16
- 14 "no fixed address\$".ti,bt. 4
- 15 ((unstabl* or un-stabl* or instability or insecur* or vulnerab*) adj2 (housed or housing)).ti,bt. 541
- 16 (temporary adj2 (accommodation or shelter*)).ti,bt. 55
- 17 ((women* or violence) adj2 (shelter* or refuge or refuges)).ti,bt. 157
- 18 "housing first".ti,bt. 238
- 19 1 or 2 or 3 or 4 or 5 or 6 or 7 or 8 or 9 or 10 or 11 or 12 or 13 or 14 or 15 or 16 or 17
- or 18 14804 [people experiencing homelessness search terms]

20 (metaanalysis or meta-analysis or metasynthesis or meta-synthesis).ti,ab.
319507

21 (systematic adj (review or overview or search*)).ti,ab. 392751

22 (systematically adj (review* or search*)).ab. 51352

23 evidence synthesis.ti,ab. 9140

24 thematic synthesis.ti,ab. 2375

25 (evidence adj2 map*).ti,ab. 2553

26 (qualitative adj2 synthesis).ti,ab. 7364

27 meta-ethnography.ti,ab. 827

28 ((mixed-stud* or (mixed adj stud*) or (mixed adj method*) or mixed-method*)
adj2 review).ti,ab. 1917

29 cochrane.jw. 17453

30 campbell.jw. 520

31 systematic reviews.jn. 3297

32 systematic review/ 312415

33 20 or 21 or 22 or 23 or 24 or 25 or 26 or 27 or 28 or 29 or 30 or 31 or 32 [systematic
review] 575528

34 19 and 33 [homelessness systematic reviews] 391

35 exp randomized controlled trial/ 654313

36 controlled clinical trial.pt. 95767

37 randomized.ab. 722194

38 placebo.ab. 264721

39 clinical trials as topic/ 206304

40 randomly.ab. 475577

41 trial.ti. 353585

42 35 or 36 or 37 or 38 or 39 or 40 or 41 [2023 Cochrane sensitivity precision
maximising filter] 1736350

43 19 and 42 [homelessness RCTs] 867

44 exp case-control studies/ or controlled before-after studies/ or interrupted time series analysis/ or exp clinical trial/ or comparative study/ 4236118

45 ("pre post" or "pre test*" or pretest* or posttest* or "post test*" or (pre adj2 post)).tw. 171941

46 (("quasi experiment*" or quasiexperiment* or "quasi random*" or quasirandom* or "quasi control*" or quasicontrol*) adj2 (method* or stud* or design*)).tw. 22952

47 ((interrupted adj time) or (non adj (randomised or randomized)) or nonequivalent or nonrandomised or nonrandomized).ti,ab. 51078

48 ((before adj2 after) or "BA stud*" or "CBA stud*").tw. 380027

49 observational study.pt. or cohort studies/ or follow-up studies/ or exp longitudinal studies/ or prospective studies/ or retrospective studies/ or cross-sectional studies/ 3340899

50 ((pilot or feasibility) adj (stud* or trial*)).ti,ab. 175797

51 ((cross-sectional or cohort or observational) adj stud*).ti,ab. 968025

52 (retrospective* adj (stud* or analysis)).ti,ab. 422907

53 49 or 50 or 51 or 52 3903156

54 control groups/ 2153

55 ((control* and group) or compar*).ti,ab. 8129411

56 54 or 55 8130287

57 53 and 56 [observational studies with a control group] 1578886

58 Outcome Assessment, Health Care/ 85252

59 evaluation study.pt. 268538

60 "evaluation studies as topic"/ 122493

61 program evaluation/ 69927

62 (program* adj evaluation).ti,ab. 6116

63 (impact adj evaluation).ti,ab. 1429

64 intervention*.ti. 246377

65 44 or 45 or 46 or 47 or 48 or 57 or 58 or 59 or 60 or 61 or 62 or 63 or 64 [other evaluation studies, non randomized, quasi, observational with a control group] 5808651

66 19 and 65 [homelessness non-RCTs and other evaluations] 3440

67 *economics/ 10827

68 exp *"costs and cost analysis"/ 87902

69 (cost minimi* or cost-utilit* or health utilit* or economic evaluation* or economic review* or cost outcome or cost analys?s or economic analys?s or budget* impact analys?s).ti,ab,kf,kw. 50494

70 (cost-effective* or pharmacoeconomic* or pharmaco-economic* or cost-benefit or costs).ti,kf,kw. 101928

71 (life year or life years or qaly* or cost-benefit analys?s or cost-effectiveness analys?s).ab,kf,kw. 50177

72 (cost or economic*).ti,kf,kw. and (costs or cost-effectiveness).ab. 86176

73 67 or 68 or 69 or 70 or 71 or 72 [cost - EE terms, CDA narrow filter] 239075

74 19 and 73 [homelessness and cost studies] 209

75 (qualitative* or interview* or experiences or (focus adj group*)).ti,ab. 1083339

76 experience.ti. 243070

77 qualitative research/ 112835

78 focus groups/43648

79 75 or 76 or 77 or 78 [qualitative studies] 1309065

80 19 and 79 [homelessness and qualitative studies] 4218

81 34 or 43 or 66 or 74 or 80 7083

Key:

/ indicates a MeSH term

.ti indicates a search in the title field

.ab. indicates a search in the abstract field

.bt. indicates a search in the book title field

*/\$ indicates a wildcard or truncation (used to search for variant word endings, or singular/plural versions of words)

.kf. or .kw. indicates a search in keyword fields

.tw. indicates a search in both the title and abstract field.